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Abstract

The sharing of software through public repositories is crucial for making sure that methodological innovations are usable by others. Software has been developed as part of the project to allow streaming of selected channels or processing outputs through the SeedLink protocol, which makes those streams immediately accessible for ingestion into EIDA archives and to be integrated into monitoring workflows. In geoscience, software development focussed on automatic picking of P and S arrival times of local and regional earthquakes, and extension of an existing standard software platform to be able to process DAS data. In oceanography, prototype software was developed to analyse the imprint of oceanic surface gravity waves on DAS cables in the shallow near-shore section and extract information on wave height extrema, dominant periods and apparent current direction.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the open-source software developed within the SUBMERSE project for the analysis and processing of submarine Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS). Software outputs span three domains — data ingestion, geoscience, and oceanography/cetology — and have been designed in accordance with open science and FAIR principles, building upon established community platforms wherever possible.

In the area of data ingestion, a SeedLink plugin for the ASN OptoDAS interrogator was jointly developed and integrated into the widely used SeisComP framework. This plugin enables real-time streaming of spatially subsampled, decimated DAS data in standard miniSEED format, making it directly compatible with existing seismological observatory workflows and suitable for data distribution via the European Integrated Data Archive (EIDA). The plugin has been deployed at multiple SUBMERSE sites and has already been adopted beyond the project.

For geoscience applications, the project evaluated and extended existing machine learning tools for seismic phase picking on submarine DAS data. A global annotated submarine DAS benchmark dataset of submarine DAS earthquake records was assembled, and a dedicated deep learning picker — DeepSubDAS — was developed and published, demonstrating superior performance over models trained with land data. DeepSubDAS has been integrated into SeisBench, a leading community platform for machine learning in seismology, enabled by an extension of SeisBench implementing efficient handling of multi-channel submarine DAS data sets. Additionally, tools were developed to use DAS data with the SSA2py software, which carries out backprojection of seismic waveforms for seismic source analysis.

In oceanography and cetology, prototype software was developed for two applications: automated location of fin whale vocalisations using hyperbolic travel-time fitting along DAS cables, and a processing workflow to extract ocean surface gravity wave parameters — including incident wave angle, dominant periods, and apparent current velocities — from DAS recordings. Both tools include worked examples.

Together, these software contributions provide the wider community with practical, interoperable instruments for exploiting submarine DAS data across seismological monitoring, ocean observation, and marine mammal research.

1 Introduction

Software developed within this project represents a key pathway for lasting scientific and operational impact. By making tools, workflows, and methods openly available, the project extends its reach beyond the immediate consortium, enabling the wider community to reproduce, validate, and build upon the work conducted here.

The software produced spans a broad spectrum of maturity. At one end, Jupyter notebooks and worked examples serve as transparent, reproducible records of the analyses underpinning project findings — lowering the barrier to entry for researchers wishing to apply similar methods to their own data. At the other end, more mature contributions have been integrated directly into established community platforms and libraries, embedding project innovations into tools that are already in active use across the seismological community.

Rather than developing bespoke solutions from the ground up, the project has deliberately built upon and extended existing community-supported packages. This approach reduces long-term maintenance burden, promotes interoperability, and ensures that project outputs remain accessible and usable beyond the funding period. Major tools and platforms include **SeisComp**, which has become a de-facto standard for seismic observatories for seismological data acquisition and real-time processing, **SeisBench**, a platform for enabling the application of machine learning workflows to seismological time series and also includes a repository of ready-made data benchmark data sets, itself building on top of PyTorch and ObsPy; and **xdas** for handling DAS datasets in an efficient and convenient manner.

The **simpleDAS** package, which is provided by interrogator supplier and project participant ASN, was used for basic data processing tasks, as demonstrated in some project-generated notebooks. Finally, **SSA2py** as a focussed package for backprojection analysis for seismic source location was used to enable backprojection analysis of the SUBMERSE-acquired DAS data. Together, these software outputs — whether a concise analysis notebook or a contributed module in a community library — reflect the project's commitment to open science and FAIR principles.

2 Software for data ingestion

2.1 Introduction: The SeisComp ecosystem and EIDA

The SeisComp¹ ecosystem is a comprehensive, open-source seismological software framework originally developed at the GFZ, and later co-developed with gempa GmbH, which has become one of the most widely deployed platforms in earthquake observatories worldwide. At its core, SeisComp provides a modular, message-oriented architecture built around a central messaging system and a relational database backend, enabling seamless integration of data acquisition, processing, archiving, and dissemination within a single, cohesive environment.

The European Integrated Data Archive (EIDA) (Strollo et al., 2021) is operated as a federated data centre as part of ORFEUS² (Observatories and Research Facilities for European Seismology). It consists of 13 nodes, generally national data centres. Many EIDA nodes, including the EIDA nodes operated by SUBMERSE partners NOA in Greece, and UiB in Norway as well as candidate EIDA node IPMA in Portugal, rely on SeisComp's data acquisition and management capabilities to ingest, quality-check, and serve waveform data. SeisComp supports the SeedLink protocol as its standard ingestion for real-time continuous data. A shortcut towards making data from the SUBMERSE DAS interrogators usable by the seismological community is thus to enable data transmission by SeedLink from the interrogator or a server in the landing station directly to earthquake observatories and seismological data archives. The data ingested this way can also be made immediately available for earthquake monitoring services, either using the built-in SeisComp earthquake monitoring module, or through other software, such as Seisan³.

Section 2.2 briefly reviews the SeedLink protocol and describes the developed software, which leverages the OptoDAS ZeroMQ streaming and the existing SeisComp library to enable streaming by SeedLink, thus providing an easy access using access tools and authentication mechanisms familiar to the seismological community, in particular, the standardised FDSN web services. Procedures are in place to restrict data access to trusted individuals, with full control of data owners on who can access the data sets. As EIDA and ORFEUS are integral parts of the Seismology Thematic Core Service (TCS) of EPOS-ERIC, the waveform data, or decimated subsets, will thus be accessible through the EPOS data portal⁴. Section 2.3 describes the implementation of this solution both at SUBMERSE sites, and its impact outside SUBMERSE.

It is important to note that this solution does not target a transfer of the full resolution data, for which the data centres of the NRENs are responsible (see Deliverable D1.5).

2.2 SeedLink plugin

The large data rate from DAS interrogation of long fibre optic cables combined with the storage format for raw data (generally HDF5), initially makes the measurement not well suited for real-time transmission and limits interoperability with conventional seismic data in earthquake observatories and tsunami early warning centres. An efficient and integrated data acquisition is required especially for the real-time applications envisaged in the

¹ <https://www.seiscomp.de/>

² <https://www.orfeus-eu.org/>

³ <https://seisan.info/>

⁴ <https://www.epos-eu.org/dataportal>

project. ASN and GFZ jointly developed the tools and interfaces needed to enable real-time decimated streaming in standard seismological data format miniSEED⁵ using the SeedLink protocol⁶.

SeedLink is an application-level protocol (TCP based) for the real-time transfer of time series data from seismological and environmental applications. A time series is represented as a sequence of packets of variable length and is identified by a station and stream ID. All connections are initiated by the client. During the handshaking phase, the client can subscribe to specific stations and streams. When handshaking is complete, a stream of SeedLink "packets" is sent to the client, consisting of an 8-byte SeedLink header followed by a 512-byte miniSEED record. A SeedLink plugin is a small program that sends data to the SeedLink server. Data supplied by a plugin can be in the form of miniSEED packets or just raw integer samples with accompanying timing information.

The ASN OptoDAS system supports ZeroMQ, a popular lightweight messaging system, to transmit real-time messages/data. The OptoDAS configuration interface allows users to set up a decimation pipeline to the SeedLink plug-in. The first message contains the measurement parameters formatted as JSON (header). Subsequent messages contain a timestamp followed by raw data bytes. Samples are natively 16-bit integers, so they fit into standard MiniSEED with Steim2 compression.

We developed the SeisComP_OptoDas plugin which maps the data received as ZeroMQ messages from the OptoDAS to MiniSEED channels according to the following scheme: network code = DAS experiment/fibre ID; station code = DAS channel; location code = usually empty (possible uses: track DAS acquisition configuration changes; (perspectively: designate components of the data corresponding to different internal pre-processing steps, e.g., spatial integration, F-K filtering, different downsampling rates, etc); channel code = HSF (for 100 Hz data). In the case that any measurement setup is changed, an updated JSON header with the new parameters will be sent to already connected subscribers. The processing chain and data flow is visualised in Figure 2.1. Supporting tools to automatically define SeisComP configuration files from the OptoDAS measurement configuration were also developed to support new users.

To enable a data stream rate compatible with standard nodal sensors, the procedure implies a strong reduction of data quantities through spatial subsampling and temporal decimation. The reduced data sets will be less sensitive than the full data set, but the decimation and filtering pre-processing steps can be customized to preserve application-specific information. See Figure 2.2 for an example of channels from a SUBMERSE site being acquired by a standard SeisComP system.

Whereas regular spacings of streamed channels of streamed channels are the default, there is the option to hand-pick channels for streaming, e.g., those ones with particularly good coupling and favourable signal-to-noise ratio, or to have denser measurements in particular areas of interest.

⁵ miniSEED is the standard format for seismological data exchange. http://www.fdsn.org/pdf/SEEDManual_V2.4.pdf

⁶ <https://www.seiscomp.de/doc/apps/seedlink.html#seedlink>

Figure 2.1 Visualisation of real-time processing and data flow to data archives. The data flow is supported by pre-processing in the DAS interrogator software and the SeedLink protocol. The pre-processing of the high-data rate DAS input enables noise suppression, decimation and decomposition to optimize the data stream for seismological workflows and further analysis in SeisComP.

Figure 2.2 Example of display in SeisComP's scrttv view of the channels streaming from the interrogator installed in Preveza, Greece.

Name	OptoDAS seedlink plugin
Developers and Contributors	Andres Heinloo, Angelo Strollo, JanPetter Morten
Purpose	Receive data streamed from ASN OptoDAS instrument
Documentation	https://www.seiscomp.de/doc/apps/seedlink.html#seedlink-sources-optodas-label
Source code	https://github.com/SeisComp/seedlink/tree/main/plugins/optodas_plugin

2.3 Use cases, community uptake and outlook

Initial testing of the SeisComp OptoDas plug-in has been carried out at the Madeira GeoLab site and one initial example dataset including the decimated data product in miniSEED, full resolution raw data in HDF5 and metadata in the candidate standard JSON format⁷ are available for this subset of data at the GEOFON EIDA node at <https://dx.doi.org/10.14470/8K802502>. (Figure 2.3).

The plugin was deployed on most of the SUBMERSE sites, with spatial sampling and decimation adapted to the requirements and security context of each site (Table 2.1). The plugin is thus demonstrated to be ready for the acquisition of decimated real-time streams. Decimated MiniSEED data from Svalbard, Preveza and sites in Portugal are now being integrated at corresponding EIDA national nodes according to DAS data management guidelines⁸ developed with the Geo-INQUIRE project.

Figure 2.3 Screenshots from the EPOS data portal and ORFEUS-EIDA interactive data portals showing the actual integration of the Madeira Geolab test site decimated miniSEED data.

More complex pre-processing involving the combination of multiple channels for generating a single output channel is also possible. This functionality can be used to reduce the noise on the subsampled output channels, e.g., through F-k filtering, or to make the data look more similar to classic seismic data, e.g., by integrating along the channel direction to convert from strain rate to velocity (for straight cable segment), increasing the ability to apply standard automated approaches for picking earthquakes and making them visually more similar to classic data stream from seismological sensors, thus increasing their utility for earthquake monitoring or other dedicated monitoring use cases.

⁷ <https://docs.fdsn.org/projects/das-metadata/en/draft/index.html>

⁸ https://orfeus.readthedocs.io/en/latest/das_guidelines.html

Beyond SUBMERSE, the plugin was adopted directly at several temporary and continuous installations, for example for an onland temporary experiment in Taiwan in 2025, and in the GONAF-Marine and GONAF-Urban fibre optic cable onshore and offshore Istanbul (Princes Islands) in the SAFAtor project. Furthermore, it has made the community aware of the power and simplicity of this approach, and SeedLink streaming has been implemented for the PRAT cable in Chile by the Chilean Seismological Service (CSN) and Geoazur as part of the ABYSS project (ERC project Diane Rivet).

Other DAS interrogator manufacturers like Silixa have realised the demand for such a plugin and offer an option to stream acquired channels in SeedLink format.

Site	Data Centre	#channels streamed	Sampling Rate (Hz)	Channel spacing (km)	Network Code & Link
Preveza, Greece (Ionian Link)	NOA	141	100	1.02	ZQ https://bbnet.gein.noa.gr/Stations_info/das-preveza_stations_status.html
Crotone, Italy (Ionian Link)	OGS	141	100	1.02	
Rhodes, Greece (COSMOTE Link)	NOA	40	100	1	HL
GeoLab, Funchal, Madeira (EllaLink)	IPMA	28	125	2	31 https://fdsn.org/networks/detail/31_2023/
Sines, Portugal (EllaLink)	IPMA	5	400	irregular	
Svalbard	UiB	1	40	-	ZP_2025 https://www.fdsn.org/networks/detail/ZP_2025/

Table 2.1 List of SUBMERSE sites, where the DAS SeedLink server, was deployed, with parameters describing the distribution

3 Geoscience software

3.1 Evaluation of existing software for earthquake analysis

The applicability of machine learning (ML) based phase pickers to offshore Preveza DAS data was systematically evaluated using pre-trained models available in **SeisBench** (Woollam et al., 2022), i.e., models trained on classic seismological 3-component data. In particular, the performance of **PhaseNet** (Zhu and Beroza, 2019) was assessed using DAS-derived strain-rate measurements. The data was resampled to 100 Hz and organized as virtual seismic stations to ensure compatibility with conventional seismic processing workflows. In order to use the 3-channels PhaseNet, the single DAS channel is simply presented three times. Surprisingly, the performance is nevertheless adequate.

Figure 3.1 presents the results of applying the PhaseNet picker to an example event, with weight sets based on training with different land seismological benchmark datasets (as stored on the SeisBench platform). The performance varies strongly depending on which weight sets were utilised. For example, PhaseNet with “geofon” pick weights are optimised for regional and teleseismic events, and thus fail to recognise the high frequency arrivals on local DAS records. Other pick weights are only sensitive to the P wave (blue in Figure 3.1) or frequently confuse P and S waves.

Among the tested models, **DiTing** (Zhao et al., 2022) exhibited the most robust performance not only for the event shown in Figure 3.1, but across a whole range of test events, providing consistent and reliable identification of both P- and S-phase arrivals. These findings agree with recent studies on other datasets (e.g., Chile, Baillet et al. 2025). A decision threshold of 0.3 was selected as an optimal trade-off between detection sensitivity and false-positive rates. The model **PhaseNet-DAS** (Zhu et al., 2023) was not considered in this analysis, as it is trained for channel spacings of 8–10 m, which is not compatible with the virtual-station configuration adopted in this study, but see section 3.2 for example of training and application of an ML picker for multi-channels submarine DAS data. The results demonstrate that the combination Seisbench-PhaseNet-DiTing can be effectively applied to offshore DAS data, provided that appropriate preprocessing steps are implemented.

Figure 3.1 Example seismic event from the Preveza DAS dataset as picked from PhaseNet with various models.

The presence of secondary seismic phases, potentially associated with sedimentary layering and complex subsurface structures (Trabattoni et al. 2024), introduces additional challenges. Under such conditions, the performance of current ML pickers is reduced, leading to increased residuals and decreased reliability. This highlights the need for further validation and potential model adaptation to improve robustness in complex geological settings. Finally, a joint event detection framework was implemented by integrating DAS virtual stations (processed using DiTing) with an onshore seismic network employing PhaseNet and Instance dataset. Application of this approach for the period March-June 2025 resulted in the detection of a larger number of seismic events compared to the catalog of the National Observatory of Athens (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2 Comparison of earthquake distributions from March to June 2025, obtained by routine processing of NOA (blue circles) and taking into account the DAS virtual stations (orange circles), combined with land stations where recorded on both. The joint event detections surpassed the NOA catalog's performance and demonstrated the extended sensing capabilities of submarine cables. Far from the cable, only larger event can be recorded, whereas near the cable very small events down to M_0 could be located.

In addition to phase picking, event location capabilities were investigated using backprojection techniques implemented within **SSA2py** (Fountoulakis and Evangelidis, 2025). SSA2py is an open-source, Python-based software package that implements the Source Scanning Algorithm (SSA) for imaging the spatiotemporal evolution of earthquake sources or/and event location. This approach aims to support near-real-time earthquake location using offshore DAS arrays. The methodology involves the construction of subarrays from DAS virtual stations to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio. Characteristic functions, such as kurtosis, are computed from the processed signals and subsequently backprojected to identify the most likely source locations. It is designed for high-performance computing (CPU and GPU), enabling fast backprojection analyses even for large datasets. The tool integrates seismic data acquisition (e.g., FDSN web services, SeedLink), performs waveform quality control, and provides uncertainty estimation through statistical methods such as bootstrap and jackknife. Overall, SSA2py supports both detailed post-event source studies and near-real-time earthquake characterization. Our initial tests indicate that the current implementation is not capable of handling the large volumes of DAS data during the preprocessing stage. Consequently, *xdas* tools were employed for data preprocessing and data reduction. Python tools were prepared for transforming DAS data into SSA2py-compatible formats for earthquake event location. The workflow supports experimental offshore event location by constructing DAS subarrays to improve SNR, computing characteristic functions such as kurtosis, and preparing the processed data for SSA2py backprojection analysis. Subsequently, the core components of SSA2py were able to successfully process the preprocessed datasets. This outcome highlights the potential for further development, particularly through the integration of DAS-specific preprocessing workflows (e.g., via *xdas*)

directly into the existing framework. Figure 3.3 shows an example of the successful application of this technique to an earthquake on the Kefalonia Transform Fault zone.

Name		DAS_to_SSA2py
Developers and Contributors	Fountouloukakis, Ioannis and Evangelidis, Christos	
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate DAS subarrays/segments based on cable geometry • Perform preprocessing (e.g., filtering, normalization, characteristic function computation) and converting DAS data into SSA2py-compatible formats for backprojection-based event location 	
Source code & Documentation	https://github.com/ifountoul/DAS_to_SSA2py	

Figure 3.3 Seismic event location using backprojection approach with SS2py code, applied to the Preveza DAS data.

3.2 Annotated global benchmark dataset

In order to develop automated, machine-learning based tools for earthquake analysis, it is necessary to train them in a variety of environments and with different interrogators, so that they do not end up overfitting specific properties of the cable. The data generated by SUBMERSE sites are not yet sufficient to provide a sufficiently diverse training set.

Therefore, we cooperated with scientists having operated DAS interrogators at various submarine cables in order to collect a large number of earthquake records (Figure 3.4). This data set incorporates data from SUBMERSE sites GeoLab in Madeira and Svalbard, but because the dataset was assembled in the first phase of the project, data from other sites were not yet flowing or accessible.

Figure 3.4 (a) Map showing the locations of all Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) cables assembled in the benchmark dataset. Each red dot represents the position of a fibre optic cable. (b) The largest data set is from the southern coastal region of Alaska, with two black lines marking the positions of the TERRA and 2KKFL-S DAS fibres. Earthquake locations are depicted by circles, with colour indicating depth and size representing magnitude. (c) Another primary data set comes from the Chilean coastline, where three cables CCN.N, SER.S and SER.N are shown by black lines alongside earthquake locations. (d) The locations of two DAS cables and corresponding earthquake locations in the Canary Islands. (e) The DAS cable and earthquake locations in Kamaishi, Japan.

To ensure the quality and accuracy of our annotations, we adopted a semi-automatic labelling approach. Initially, we applied PhaseNet (Zhu & Beroza 2018), using the SeisBench (Münchmeyer *et al.* 2022; Woollam *et al.* 2022) platform, to perform single-channel labelling, leveraging its efficiency in identifying *P* and *S* seismic waves. We applied a bandpass frequency filter in the range of 0.5 to 20 Hz, as well as an FK (frequency–wavenumber) filter with a slowness window corresponding to apparent velocities between 300 and 50 000 m/s. Whereas in many cases, this simplistic approach already resulted in reasonable picks, there were also many instances where the no arrival was identified, *P* and *S* waves were not identified correctly, or the wrong part of the waveform was

picked. Therefore, to enhance the reliability of these labels, we developed an interactive software tool that allows manual correction of labelling results. We manually intervened every 5–10 channels, depending on the channel spacing for each DAS cable, correcting errors that might have arisen due to excessive noise on single-component DAS data. The arrival times of the *P* and *S* waves for the channels in between were determined through linear interpolation. We also conducted manual checks to ensure the accuracy of these interpolated times, and if any discrepancies were found, we intervened and corrected them manually. This hybrid method enabled us to efficiently and accurately label *P*- and *S*-wave seismic records, ensuring more accurate labelled data for subsequent analysis. To enhance our data set and improve the stability of our model, we augmented the data by incorporating real oceanic DAS seismic noise. These noise samples were carefully selected, ensuring that they were recorded during periods without seismic events.

3.3 DeepSubDAS picker

Nearly all published machine learning models for picking seismic phases operate on three components at a single site. Only, very few models exist that work directly on multichannel DAS data. PhaseNetDAS (Zhu et al. 2023), the existing machine learning model trained on land-based DAS data does not perform well with submarine DAS due to differences in noise characteristics, deployment conditions and environmental factors. This study presents a machine learning approach tailored specifically to submarine DAS data to enable automated seismic event detection and *P*- and *S*-wave identification. Leveraging DeepLab v3, a neural network architecture optimized for semantic segmentation, we developed a specialized model, DeepSubDAS to handle the unique challenges of submarine DAS data (Figure 3.5). Our model was trained and validated on the data set described in section 3.2. The model adapts to a variety of deployment scenarios and can process DAS data from cables with different lengths, configurations and channel spacings, making it versatile for various ocean environments. Figure 3.6 shows a comparison of results of the DeepSubDAS picker with those of PhaseNetDAS, which was trained on land seismic data, demonstrating the superior performance on marine seismic data. On the benchmark test data set typical picking errors were about ± 0.25 s, comparable to typical estimated picking errors of the semiautomatic picks (Figure 3.7). We thus provide an adaptable and efficient tool for automated earthquake analysis of DAS data, which has the potential to enhance real-time earthquake monitoring and tsunami early warning in submarine environments. Finally, Figure 3.8 shows the application of this picker to data acquired at the SUBMERSE Preveza site.

Both benchmark dataset and the machine learning picker training and evaluation are described in *Geophysical Journal International* publication by Xiao et al (2026).

Figure 3.5 Illustration of DeepLab v3 model architecture as applied to submarine DAS data. The data is treated equivalently to an image in a standard DeepLab v3 model, with channel number representing one dimension, and time representing another dimension, and the algorithm is trained to segment this image probabilistically into pixels corresponding to P arrivals, pixels corresponding to S arrivals, and pixels containing no arrival.

Figure 3.6 Comparison of performance of DeepSubDAS (left panels) with baseline PhaseNetDAS (Zhu et al, 2023) (right panels). DeepSubDAS is less prone to phase misidentifications (a and b) or spurious picks (c) and shows typically higher precision (d).

Figure 3.7 Detection and picking performance for the different benchmark datasets. In the table, the F1 score combines the precision and recall for the optimal threshold value. MAE: Median Absolute Error.

Figure 3.8 Example application of DeepSubDAS to data acquired at the SUBMERSE Preveza site (ISLALINK cable). Left panel: Regional earthquake. M 6.0 - 20 km SSE of Fry, Greece. 2025-05-13 22:51:15 (UTC), 35.237°N 26.995°E, Depth: 76.2 km, distance to cable: ~750 km. The picks are generally good, except that some common mode noise is erroneously picked as P arrival (channels 10500-12000, ~12 s). Right panel: Local earthquake M 4.1 - 20 km WSW of Lefkáda, Greece, 2025-04-12 23:38:13 (UTC), 38.781°N 20.474°E, Depth: 10.0 km, Distance to cable: ~60 km. There are some missed picks at larger distances, and a later arriving wavetrain, probably the surface wave from the event, is erroneously identified as S wave. Note that a channel offset of 1000 corresponds to about 10 km horizontal distance.

Name		DeepSubDAS
Developers and Contributors	Han Xiao, Frederik Tilmann, Afonso Loureiro (SUBMERSE contributors) + Martijn van den Ende, Diane Rivet, Takeshi Tsuji, Arantza Ugalde, Qibin Shi and Marine, A. Denolle	
Purpose	Annotate continuous full resolution streams of submarine DAS data with P and S arrival times	
Publication	Xiao H., Tilmann, F., van den Ende, M., Rivet D., Loureiro, A., Tsuji, T., Ugalde, A., Shi Q., Denolle, M. A., DeepSubDAS: An Earthquake Phase Picker Submarine Distributed Acoustic Sensing Data <i>Geophys. J. Int.</i> , 245 , https://doi.org/10.1093/gji/ggag061	
Source code	https://zenodo.org/records/19002976	
Benchmark dataset	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16014744 (example set) ⁹	

3.4 SeisBench DAS integration

The SeisBench (Seismology Benchmark collection; Woollam et al. 2022) is an open-source python toolbox for machine learning in seismology. It provides a unified API for accessing seismic datasets and models, enabling users to both train machine learning models with a range of benchmark datasets and apply machine learning algorithms for seismic data. SeisBench has been built to reduce the overhead when applying or developing machine learning techniques for seismological tasks.

Previously, SeisBench was only able to work with 3- or 4-component time series from seismometers and ocean bottom seismometers, respectively. This functionality could already be applied so submarine DAS data as acquired by SUBMERSE by considering individual channels, which can work reasonably well (see section 3.1), but does not use the coherency of channels.

Through the SUBMERSE project, the functionality of SeisBench was extended to be able to deal with multi-channel DAS data in a way that allows a neural network to operate on a patch of the 'waterfall' data representation and segment it as explained in section 3.3 for the DAS into seismic P- and S arrival and 'noise/other' classes and finally generate picks based on peaks of the segmentation pseudo-probability function, if above a certain threshold.

Specifically, SeisBench offers an abstract class, `DASModel`¹⁰. Following the SeisBench paradigm for classical waveform data, models inheriting from this class have two interfaces. First, each model works as a regular PyTorch model, particularly useful for training the model. Second, for users wishing to apply trained models to new data sets, there are the `annotate` and `classify` functions. These functions take `xdas` DataArrays as input, allowing to process all data that can be read by `xdas`. In the background, SeisBench will take care of

⁹ The benchmark dataset is currently being integrated into the SeisBench platform and will be available for researchers for model training.

¹⁰

https://seisbench.readthedocs.io/en/stable/pages/documentation/models/base.html#seisbench.models.das_base.DASModel

chunking, reassembling, batching, and processing, optionally on a GPU, where larger-than-memory data can be handled without the user needing to get into the details of memory management.

In practice, this functionality is implemented via a range of callback functions shipped with the code. By setting up different call-back functions, the functionality can be easily extended while abstracting the data and memory handling from the user. The following code snippet demonstrates how to load and annotate a DAS dataset with pick times by using SeisBench's `annotate` method with the `DASPickingCallback`¹¹ callback:

```
data = xdas.open_dataarray("mydata")
callback = DASPickingCallback()
annotations = model.annotate(stream, callback) # Execute the model
callback.get_results_dict() # The resulting picks
```

An even simpler but less flexible interface is provided by the `classify` function, which works similarly to `annotate`, but instead of providing a callback, only the data needs to be passed to the method and the picking model will output a list of picks just as for regular SeisBench models for 3-component waveforms.

```
stream = xdas.open_dataarray("mydata")
outputs = model.classify(stream) # Returns a list of picks
print(outputs)
```

For advanced users SeisBench exposes the asynchronous implementations `annotate_async` and `classify_async` to avoid blocking the execution thread.

The DeepSubDAS model, as described in section 3.3, is available through the SeisBench DAS interface including trained weights, but the utility of the development of the SeisBench DAS interface goes far beyond making this model available to users through the familiar SeisBench platform in enabling retraining of this model as new annotated data become available and also through offering a platform for adding new models, which would operate on a unified interface. By building on `xdas`, it will also be able to straightforwardly keep up with the evolution of formats for DAS data.

In addition to providing an interface for dedicate DAS pickers, the SeisBench functionality implemented through SUBMERSE also allows an interface for application of single-channel pickers to all records at once. As shown in section 3.1, those pickers provide adequate performance in some settings, especially after multichannel preprocessing such as integration in the spatial direction to convert strain rate to velocity.

An example notebook shows how to load DAS data and apply the single channel pickers as well as the DeepSubDAS multichannel picker through the SeisBench interface.

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https://seisbench.readthedocs.io/en/stable/pages/documentation/models/base.html#seisbench.models.das_base.DASPickingCallback

Name		SeisBench: addition of DAS processing capability
Developers and Contributors	Jannes Münchmeyer	
Purpose	Implement an interface for application of machine learning models to multi-channel DAS waveform in the SeisBench platform	
Documentation	https://seisbench.readthedocs.io/en/stable/pages/data/overview.html https://seisbench.readthedocs.io/en/stable/pages/models/das_models.html	
Source code	DAS support in SeisBench https://github.com/seisbench/seisbench/releases/tag/v0.11.0 The SeisBench implementation of DeepSubDAS will be included in the next minor release (v0.12.0) of SeisBench.	
Example Notebook	https://colab.research.google.com/github/seisbench/seisbench_training/blob/main/2026_04_15_submerse.ipynb	

4 Software prototypes for oceanography and cetology applications

4.1 OptoDAS processor

Name		Optodas processor with ocean wave current proxy estimator and whale call detector/locator
Developers and Contributors	David Schlaphorst, Afonso Loureiro, Andreia Pereira, Luis Matias	
Purpose	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Load and process OptoDAS datasets. 2) Estimate significant wave heights, dominant period, propagation direction of ocean surface gravity waves and surface current velocity from DAS recordings along shallow submarine cables. 3) Using template matching to detect a fin whale vocalizing the regular note, also known as the 20 Hz note, which in fact is a down sweep from 25 to 18 Hz. 4) Locate a fin whale vocalizing. For a flat sea bottom and straight cable, the travel time from the whale to the cable follows a hyperbolic equation, which is used to detect the position of the whale with respect to the cable. 	
Publication	Schlaphorst, D., Matias, L. M., Loureiro, A., Papapostoulou, A., Corela, C., Gonçalves, S., & Caldeira, R. (2026). Non-peer reviewed Report submitted to Seismica: Correlation of DAS Strain Data and Oceanographic Variables in the North-East Atlantic. https://eartharxiv.org/repository/view/12217/	
Source code & Documentation	https://github.com/speleos/OptoDAS_processor/blob/v0.2-alpha https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19856965 (v0.2 alpha)	

4.1.1 Basics

A Python Class was developed to handle OptoDAS data. It leverages the existing `simpleDAS` framework¹², but extends it with time lapse processing, conversion to multiple formats, travel time corrections, and signal processing tools.

The processing steps are defined on a per-event basis, with the relevant parameters loaded from a sources list. Global variables are set in a config file, but can be overridden, if appropriate. This architecture allows the user to define parameters for plotting a figure, for example, and save them for later use. Data loading can be windowed in both time and space, and multiple channels need not be contiguous. A loosely integrated baleen whale detector based on template matching and tools for locating the source of vocalisations are also provided. A description of the application of this code follows in the next section.

¹² <https://github.com/ASN-Norway/simpleDAS>

4.1.2 Ocean surface gravity wave properties

For DAS recordings on the shallow shelf, the imprint of ocean surface gravity waves (OSGW) is often the dominant signal in unfiltered records.

The amplitude of the DAS signal is related to the height of the ocean waves, with the proportionality different for each channel, with generally shallower water depths and more compliant seafloor resulting in larger amplitudes. Therefore, each cable would require careful calibration before it can be used to estimate absolute significant wave heights. The dominant period of the DAS signal corresponds to the dominant wave period. The dispersion relation of incoming and outgoing waves provides information on the direction of ocean waves with respect to the cable, with more oblique directions resulting in faster apparent velocities. In addition, if a surface current carries the waves along with respect to the stationary cable, the dispersion curves for seaward and landward propagation are skewed. It is therefore possible to estimate wave propagation direction and current velocity from the apparent dispersion along the cable.

We provide a demonstration script as part of the OptoDAS processor collection that carries out the analysis for these ocean parameters (or more precisely their proxies) from DAS recordings of ocean gravity waves. The following processing sequence is followed (see Figure 4.1):

1. Downsample data to 1 Hz.
2. Apply 2-d Fourier transform into the F-k domain; this divides the data into two halves, one including all movement landward (positive k) along the cable and one seaward (negative k).
3. Detect the strongest amplitudes per frequency on land- and seaward side
4. Create theoretical dispersion curves of synthetic OSGW, including influences from ocean currents (parameter 1) and wave train incidence angles with respect to the cable (parameter 2).
5. Vary the two parameters in a grid search to find the best solution to describe the data.

Figure 4.1 Example of oceanic wave dispersion for one half-hour file of data on channels 460 to 560. (a) Detected points of high amplitude created from the dispersion data. (b) Misfit grid search. (c) Dispersion data with detected points, as well as theoretical dispersion curves for the values found in the grid search at seafloor depths of 5 and 13 m (depth interval for the channels used here), as well as point detection limits imposed by the procedure. (d) Dispersion data and best fit theoretical dispersion curves.

As an example, we observe the ocean state south of Madeira Island in the Atlantic using a week of data from a DAS fibre-optic cable (Figure 4.2). To verify the results, the data were compared with measurements from an adjacent buoy and the predictions of a wave model. We use a buoy which has a distance to the cable of less than 1 km. We require strong amplitudes to observe the dispersion curves of OSGWs. Therefore, we concentrate on the first marine channels close to the coast on the shallow shelf, which have a high signal-to-noise ratio, and we take a spatial interval of about 500 m (channels 460 to 560) and use half-hour intervals of data. The distance interval is limited due to the steep bathymetry around the island; the time interval is limited due to general variation of the sea state over time.

Figure 4.2 Results of DAS observations against oceanographic parameters for the 7-day period in 2023. (A) Oceanic current from DAS dispersion curve fitting against tide values. Blue stars show individual 30-minute measurements, the black line show a rolling 5 measurement average. Red crosses show tidal values for Funchal, which is close to the landing site of the cable, grey lines show sine interpolations between those values. (B) Dominant wave incidence angle from DAS dispersion curve fitting against tide values. (C) Maximum amplitude values of landward waves against SWH (arrow amplitude) and mean wave direction (arrow direction). The measurements are taken from the closely located buoy (red for western and blue for eastern directions) and from the IBI data (grey). (D) Maximum amplitude values of seaward waves against tide values. (Schlaphorst et al. 2026 -preprint).

4.2 Whale call location

Given a set of simplifying hypotheses: (i) The whale is vocalizing close to the surface so that in practice we use zero depth; (ii) The cable is linear in the range that is recording the whale sound. This means that the whale is located along a line orthogonal to the channel that records the earliest time of the vocalization; (iii) The cable depth is constant, equal to the depth of the closest channel to the sound source; (iv) The sound velocity is constant, and sound propagation is linear; then the sound travel time from the whale to a linear cable should follow an hyperbola. This hyperbola is a function of the coordinates of the apex, both in space and time, and the

distance to the cable. The code uses a systematic search on these three parameters. The best location (distance to the nearest cable channel and apex travel time) are found as the ones that maximize the sum of the f-k amplitudes, after building an envelope with only positive values. To begin the whale location, we need as input a data block that includes the hyperbolic image of the vocalization.

The processing sequence is as follows:

1. Load a chunk of the data. The example data provided in the repository is already truncated to a ~ 30 km x 30 s block, decimated to 100 Hz.
2. Band-pass filter the data from 10 to 40 Hz.
3. Filter the data using an f-k filter with a minimum limit of 1.4 km/s to remove the signal OSGWs and isolate sound waves in the water layer.
4. Calculate the envelope by applying a Hilbert transform.
5. Carry out a grid search for the apex and curvature of the hyperbola.
6. Sum up the amplitudes of the data along the defined curve.
7. Compare the summed amplitudes for different positions and shapes of the curve and find the best solution (highest amplitude).
8. Check the solution and save the best. These can be used later to compute the geographical coordinates of the sound source.
9. Go to step (1) for the next vocalization.

Figure 4.3 shows an example of the hyperbolic fit to the f-k amplitude diagram in red. In blue we show the first multipath as a reference. We do not expect to fit the direct ray and multipath simultaneously given the variable seafloor depth.

Figure 4.3 Waterfall plot for data block for the first vocalization example, after band-pass and f-k filtering, with hyperbolic fit for the direct wave (in red) and 1st multipath (in blue).

We recall here two hypotheses that underline the hyperbolic fitting applied above: (i) The cable is linear in the range that is recording the whale sound. This means that the whale is located along a line orthogonal to the channel that records the earliest time of the vocalization; (ii) The cable depth is constant, equal to the depth of the closest channel to the sound source.

To test assumption (i) we compute the true distance between the whale and the cable and compute the corresponding travel time. The comparison between the two travel times is shown in Figure 4.4a. To test assumption (ii) we compute the travel time considering a straight cable but the true water depth at the cable channels (Figure 4.4b). Finally, we consider the comparison with the true depth and cable geometry in Figure 4.4c.

We may conclude that for the Geolab cable the largest errors in the simple hyperbolic fit computation arise from the linearity assumption for the geometry of the cable, with difference between the simple hyperbola and the "true" travel time curve up to 0.6 s

Figure 4.4 (a) Comparison of hyperbolic travel time and travel time computed with the true distance between the whale and the cable channels with the simplifying assumption of a straight cable. Cable is assumed to be at constant depth for this comparison. (b) Comparison of hyperbolic travel time and travel time computed with the true water depth at each channel. The water depth varies by approximately 700 m across the 20 km range shown. Cable is assumed to be a straight line for this comparison. (c) Comparison with realistic cable geometry and depth.

4.3 Software prototype for visual analysis of ocean wave signals

Name	<Name of software>
Developers and Contributors	Aggeliki Barberopoulou
Purpose	Visualise submarine DAS data in time and frequency domains and produce graphics which describe the content of these data for further analysis.
Source code & documentation	https://github.com/ippolyte/ocean-das-training/

With operational oceanography in mind a workflow was implemented to process and produce content descriptions of DAS data for further analysis. There were three main objectives:

- Read DAS files
- Visualise data in both time and frequency domains
- Reduce the size of the files while keeping essential information in hand
- Process data to extract ocean wave information

The github repository provides a sample file of 1 hour which has been processed from the original optoDAS 10 s files as follows:

- Spatially downsample to reduce size of channels
- 10 s files were concatenated to 1-hour files
- Lowpass filter and downsampling from 500Hz to 50 Hz
- A second filter and downsampling stage to reduce the sample rate to 2 Hz (Figure 4.5) to reduce size of the file but also focus on ocean waves

Further processing of 1-hour records was applied as follows:

- Calculate average spectrum over all channels
- Calculate standard deviation for each channel to identify noise channels or channels of interest.
- Calculate FK spectrum to identify source of energy and separate waves of different type (ocean vs seismic; dispersion is evident in such plots)

Figure 4.5 Timeseries of strain rate recorded by the Madeira Cable (1-hour records) for 4 different channels along with their corresponding spectra and spectrograms.

5 Conclusion & Outlook

The software produced by the SUBMERSE project for the use cases in geosciences, oceanography and marine biology ranges from production-ready software plugins essential for effective data dissemination to seismological users, over still experimental software embedded in existing frameworks, accompanied by illustrative notebooks, to Proof-of-concept software, also generally in the form of notebooks. All the software developments are made available on open platforms with data examples, with a preference for github as this platform makes it very easy to further develop the software and encourage others to contribute. Most of the developed software have accompanying training units, accessible on a permanent basis through the LifeWatch training platform (see deliverable D4.4). During the sustainability phase of the SUBMERSE infrastructure past the project end, further developments will take place, as continuously operating fibre-optic sensing along submarine telecommunication cables becomes more widespread, and the software is used for active research by the original consortium members as well as the wider research community. A lesson learned from SUBMERSE has been that only a fraction of the data acquired can be fully opened up with small delay. Therefore, the next systematic step has to be to develop analysis software that can work autonomously on 'hidden' data, and produce less sensitive outputs, for example, a phase arrival picker can work on waveforms and return phase arrival picks or even earthquake locations, which can then be shared without restrictions, or the OSGW parameters are extracted from continuous DAS recordings to oceanographics databases. It is clear that additional efforts are needed beyond the proof-of-concepts successfully targeted in SUBMERSE to allow such analysis to provide reliable results without in each case being able to scrutinise the underlying waveform data. Future developments, especially when they involve machine learning (AI) based methods, rely on large quantities of sample data, so opening as much as possible submarine fiber-sensing data must be a priority for any future projects or activities.

References

- Baillet, M., Rivet, D., Trabatttoni, A., Chèze, J., Peix, F., Ambrois, D., van den Ende, M., Vernet, C., Strumia, C., Potin, B., Sánchez-Olavarría, R., & Barrientos, S. E. (2025, July 13). Automatic earthquake catalogs from a permanent DAS offshore network. ESS Open Archive. <https://doi.org/10.31223/XZY123>
- Fountoulakis, Ioannis; Christos P. Evangelidis; SSA2py: A High-Performance Python Implementation of the Source-Scanning Algorithm for Spatiotemporal Seismic Source Imaging. *Seismological Research Letters* 2024;; 95 (4): 2506–2518. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220230335>
- Schlaphorst, D., Matias, L. M., Loureiro, A., Papapostoulou, A., Corela, C., Gonçalves, S., & Caldeira, R. (2026). Non-peer reviewed Report submitted to Seismica: Correlation of DAS Strain Data and Oceanographic Variables in the North-East Atlantic. <https://eartharxiv.org/repository/view/12217/>
- Strollo, A., Cambaz, D., Clinton, J., Danecek, P., Evangelidis, C. P., Marmureanu, A., Ottemöller, L., Pedersen, H., Sleeman, R., Stammler, K., Armbruster, D., Bienkowski, J., Boukouras, K., Evans, P., Fares, M., Neagoe, C., Heimers, S., Heinloo, A., Hoffmann, M., Kaestli, P., Lauciani, V., Michalek, J., Odon Muhire, E., Ozer, M., Palangeanu, L., Pardo, C., Quinteros, J., Quintiliani, M., Antonio Jara-Salvador, J., Schaeffer, J., Schloemer, A., Triantafyllis, N. (2021): EIDA: The European Integrated Data Archive and Service Infrastructure within ORFEUS. - *Seismological Research Letters*, 92, 3, 1788-1795. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220200413>
- Trabatttoni, A., Vernet, C., van den Ende, M., Baillet, M., Potin, B., & Rivet, D. (2024). Sediment corrections for distributed acoustic sensing. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 129, e2024JB029054. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024JB029054>
- Woollam, J., Münchmeyer, J., Tilmann, F., Rietbrock, A., Lange, D., Bornstein, T., Diehl, T., Giunchi, C., Haslinger, F., Jozinović, D., Michelini, A., Saul, J., & Soto, H. (2022). SeisBench—A toolbox for machine learning in seismology. *Seismological Research Letters*, 93(3), 1695–1709. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220210324>
- Xiao H., Tilmann, F., van den Ende, M., Rivet D., Loureiro, A., Tsuji, T., Ugalde, A., Shi Q., Denolle, M. A., DeepSubDAS: An Earthquake Phase Picker Submarine Distributed Acoustic Sensing Data. *Geophys. J. Int.*, 245, <https://doi.org/10.1093/gji/ggag061>
- Zhao, M., Xiao, Z., Chen, S., & Fang, L. H. (2022). DiTing: A large-scale Chinese seismic benchmark dataset for artificial intelligence in seismology. *Earthquake Science*, 35(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eqs.2021.12.003>
- Zhu, W., Biondi, E., Li, J., Zhang, S., Sadeghisorkhani, H., Mousavi, S. M., Ruan, Y., Li, Z., Zhan, Z., & Beroza, G. C. (2023). Seismic arrival-time picking on distributed acoustic sensing data using semi-supervised learning. *Nature Communications*, 14, 8192. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-43355-3>